

MOLECULAR AND BIOCHEMICAL ANALYSIS OF ANTIOXIDANT ENZYMES IN PULMONARY TISSUE OF RATS IN EXPERIMENTAL FLUOROSIS

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ABSTRACT

Background: Fluoride toxicity is a global health problem with many countries have been declared endemic for fluorosis. Excessive accumulation of fluoride is manifested by skeletal fluorosis, dental fluorosis and various symptoms affecting non-skeletal tissues. The present study aimed to evaluate the toxicological effects of sodium fluoride (NaF) on biochemical and molecular gene expression levels of some antioxidant enzymes in the pulmonary tissue of fluoride-intoxicated rats. **Methods:** Wistar albino rats were randomly assigned to three groups. The control rats were given 1 ml deionized water orally for 40 days. Groups II and III were administered 300 and 600 mg NaF/kg b.w./day for the same period. Animals were sacrificed. The lung tissue was excised and used for biochemical and real-time PCR analysis. **Results:** The level of fluoride, malondialdehyde (MDA), reduced glutathione (GSH) and activities of different antioxidant enzymes such as cytosolic copper/zinc superoxide dismutase (Cu/Zn SOD), glutathione peroxidase (GPx) and catalase (CAT) were determined. The analysis of gene expression of different antioxidant enzymes in lung was done using Real-time PCR. The lung tissue exhibited significantly increased levels of fluoride and MDA ($P < 0.0001$), while the GSH content decreased significantly ($P < 0.0001$) in fluoridated rats. Additionally, the activities of antioxidant enzymes, including Cu/Zn SOD, GPx, and CAT, showed a significant decline ($P < 0.0001$) compared to the control group. Pearson's bivariate correlation and simple linear regression analysis revealed a strong positive correlation between lung tissue fluoride and MDA ($r = 0.993$), while negative correlations were observed in GSH ($r = -0.956$) as well as in the activities of Cu/Zn SOD ($r = -0.996$), GPx ($r = -0.994$), and CAT ($r = -0.982$). The gene expression of Cu/Zn SOD, GPx and CAT was significantly ($P < 0.0001$) reduced in fluorotic rats ($P < 0.0001$). **Conclusion:** It is concluded that fluoride intoxication induces significant oxidative stress disrupting cellular metabolism and comprising the function of free radical scavengers. The increased lipid peroxidation and the decreased expression of antioxidant genes observed in the pulmonary tissue helps to depict the molecular mechanisms underlying the fluoride induced toxicity.

KEYWORDS: Catalase, Cytosolic Copper/Zinc superoxide dismutase, Gene expression, Glutathione peroxidase, Lung, Oxidative stress.

Abbreviations: Catalase (CAT), Copper/Zinc superoxide dismutase (Cu/Zn SOD), Glutathione peroxidase (GPx), Malondialdehyde (MDA), Reactive oxygen species (ROS), Reduced glutathione (GSH), Sodium fluoride (NaF).

1. INTRODUCTION

The lung is one of the soft tissues most susceptible to fluoride intoxication, attributable to both industrial

exposure and other environmental sources. Previous studies have demonstrated high fluoride accumulation in lung tissues, leading to the respiratory system's susceptibility to fluoride toxicity.^[1-3] It is a site of major reactive oxygen species production because it has a large surface area that is constantly in contact with oxygen and pollutants. Since it is a pulmonary tissue and exhibits higher oxygen exposure than any other organ which makes it vulnerable to free-radical mediated injury.^[4]

Several studies have documented that the interaction of the lungs with reactive oxygen species (ROS) might be associated with the development of several lung diseases. The fluoride-induced oxidative stress-mediated pulmonary disease has become a global epidemic and is likely to become the third-largest cause of death worldwide.^[5-7] Prolonged exposure to fluoride hinders the activities of antioxidant enzymes and reduces GSH levels. The ratio of reduced to oxidized GSH within the cells is a major marker of cellular oxidative stress. Free radicals produced by fluoride are involved in various pathological and physiological processes in the lungs such as cell signalling, apoptosis and worsen the function of pulmonary surfactant.^[8] Oxidative stress created by excessive fluoride intake leads to disrupt the membranes of cellular compounds and damage the metabolism of the cellular system, even the genomic complexities are also observed in the previous study^[9] which leads to severe abolishes of antioxidant defence system in the lungs and leads to cell death.^[10] Study of literature has revealed that overproduction of ROS decreased the anti-inflammatory factors and anti-oxidants as increase the pro-inflammatory cytokines in the lungs of mice treated with fluoride.^[11]

In both experimental and epidemiological research involving humans, fluoride was found to be involved in eliciting respiratory disorders such as pneumoconiosis, a decrease in small airway blockage, asthma, bronchitis, and emphysema, as well as poor lung function. During prolonged fluoride exposure in experimental animals, alveolar wall breakdown, congestion, and inflammatory cell infiltration, as well as septal wall thickening were detected.^[12,13]

Fluoride has been shown to affect the expression of some genes and proteins in cell signalling pathways. Fluoride-induced oxidative stress has been shown to impact gene regulatory pathways and protein expression as well as cause DNA, protein and lipid damage.^[14] The present study aimed to expose the mechanism of fluorosis by exploring the adverse effects of NaF on oxidative stress and gene expression level of different antioxidant enzymes in Wistar albino rats.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Experimental design

The experimental study was performed on Wistar albino rats in the weight range of 150-200 g were housed in propylene cages with spotless grill tops. They were fed on standard commercial rat pellet diet (Hindustan lever limited, Mumbai, India) and water was given *ad libitum*.

Institutional Animal Ethics Committee of Punjabi University, Patiala approved all experimental procedures with experimental animals (Animal maintenance and registration number 107/GO/ReBi/S/99/CPCSEA/2017-40). Rats were divided into three groups and each group contained six rats. The animals of the group I served as control and received 1ml of deionized water orally for 40

days. The animals of group II and III were given 300 and 600 mg NaF/kg b.w./day for the same period. At the end of the experimental period, all groups of rats were fasted overnight and sacrificed.

2.2 Determination of fluoride level

The extraction^[15] and estimation^[16] of fluoride in the lung tissue was estimated on selective ion electrode (ELIT 8221).

2.3 Measurement of lipid peroxidation

The level of MDA in the lung tissue was measured by thiobarbituric acid method at the absorbance wavelength of 532 nm.^[17]

2.4 Determination of reduced glutathione level

The level of GSH was determined by the method of M. Moron.^[18]

2.5 Homogenate preparation and enzyme assays

The lung tissue was excised, washed, and perfused with normal saline to remove excess blood. It was then homogenized in 0.1M phosphate buffer (pH 7.4) and centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 15 minutes at 4°C. The resulting supernatant was used for further biochemical analysis, while some aliquots of the lung tissue were preserved in RNA laterTM (Ambion, USA) for RNA isolation and stored at -80°C for future analysis. The activity of cytosolic Cu/Zn SOD (EC: 1.15.1.1) in the lung tissue was determined in accordance with the recommendations proposed by J.F. Ewing and D.R. Janero.^[19] The activity of GPx (EC: 1.11.1.9) was assayed using the method outlined by J.T. Rotruck^[20], and the activity of CAT (EC: 1.11.1.6) was evaluated using the method of H.E. Aebi.^[21]

2.6 RNA isolation and reverse transcription

RNA was isolated using Trizol kit (G-Biosciences, USA). The isolated RNA was checked using RNA gel electrophoresis and a Nanodrop spectrophotometer (USA). cDNA was synthesized using the Reverse AidTM first strand cDNA synthesis kit (Thermo scientific, USA) according to the manufacturer's protocol.

2.7 Primers and quantitative real-time RT-PCR assay

The gene expression profile was determined using the SYBR green (Thermo Scientific, USA) based qPCR method. During qPCR, 4µl of total RNA was reverse transcribed into cDNA using 2µl of oligo (dT)18 and a reverse transcriptase kit in a final volume of 20 µl. Subsequently, 4 µl of the reaction product was used as a template for PCR with 2 µl each of Cu/Zn SOD, GPx, and CAT forward and reverse primers, with β-actin as the reference gene. The PCR reactions were performed in ABI Prism SDS 7000. Primers were selected to specifically bind to the target genes (Table 1).^[22] Co-amplification of primers with β-actin was incorporated to ensure equal RNA amounts were reverse transcribed and amplified in each reaction tube. The gene symbols and GenBank accession numbers used were Cu/Zn SOD

(NM_017050.1), GPx (NM_030826.4), CAT (NM_012520.2), and β -actin (NM_031144.3). The reaction conditions comprised an initial denaturation at 95°C for 10 minutes, followed by denaturation at 95°C for 15 seconds, annealing at 60°C for 30 seconds, extension at 72°C for 30 seconds, and a final extension at 72°C for 10 minutes – all performed over 40 cycles. The amount of target sequence in each sample was estimated

from the threshold cycle number (CT) generated on the ABI Prism SDS 7000 version 2.0. Gene expression was calculated using the $2^{-\Delta\Delta Ct}$ formula^[23], and an analysis of the dissociation curve was also conducted. The amplified products were resolved using a 1.0% agarose gel, stained with ethidium bromide, and visualized in the Gel Documentation System and photographed.

Table 1: Primer pair sets for qPCR.

Gene symbols Accession Number Primer Sequence (5'-3')			
β -actin	NM_031144.3	Forward	cctgcttctgatccaca
		Reverse	ctgaccgagcgtggctac
Cu/Zn SOD	NM_017050.1	Forward	gcagaaggcaagcgggtgaac
		Reverse	tagcaggacagcagatgagt
GPx	NM_030826.4	Forward	ctctccgcggtggcacagt
		Reverse	ccaccaccgggtcggacatac
CAT	NM_012520.2	Forward	gcgaatggagaggcagtgtac
		Reverse	gagtgacgtgtcttcattagcactg

2.8 Statistical analysis

The data was analysed using the statistical package SPSS (version 20.0 SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL, USA). Data were presented as Mean \pm SD. The statistical differences between the control and treatment groups were examined using one-way ANOVA. Multiple comparisons among all treatment groups were carried out by Post hoc Tukey's HSD test. To explore the correlation between fluoride and enzymatic activities, Pearson's bivariate

correlation and simple linear regression analysis was conducted. Results were considered significant at $p < 0.05$.

3. RESULTS

The mean weight of the lung tissue in experimental fluorosis decreased significantly ($P < 0.0001$) with respect to control (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1: The mean weight of lung (g) in rat after 40 days of fluoride exposure. The Values are represented as Mean \pm SD (n=6). ^a $P < 0.0001$ Groups II and III vs Group I, ^{a,a} $P < 0.0001$ Group II vs Group III.

3.1 Fluoride level

The mean level of fluoride in the lung of experimental rats increased significantly ($P < 0.0001$) in comparison with control group (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2: Fluoride levels in the lung of rats after 40 days of exposure. The Values are represented as Mean \pm SD (n=6). ^aP<0.0001 Groups II and III vs Group I, ^{a,a}P<0.0001 Group II vs Group III.

3.2 Oxidative stress profile

The mean level of MDA in the lung tissue of fluoride treated rats elevated significantly (P<0.0001) with respectively increasing +111.59% in group II received 300 mg/L NaF and +222.66% in group III received 600 mg/L NaF as compared with control (Fig. 3a). Post hoc Tukey's HSD multiple comparison test after ANOVA displayed a significant increase (P<0.0001) in the level of MDA between and within groups (95% CI= -1.055 to -0.980) after 40 days of fluoride intoxication.

The mean level of GSH in the lung tissue of test rats decreased significantly (P<0.0001) in comparison to control. A decrease of -45.99% in group II received 300 mg/L NaF and -67.86% in group III received 600 mg/L NaF was seen after 40 days of fluoride intoxication (Fig. 3b). Post hoc Tukey's HSD multiple comparison test after ANOVA revealed a significant decrease (P<0.0001) in GSH content between and within groups (95% CI= 1.211 to 0.736) after 40 days of fluoride exposure.

Fig. 3: a-b Oxidative biochemistry profile of MDA and GSH level in the lung of rat after 40 days of exposure to fluoride. The values represent Mean \pm SD (n=6). ^aP<0.0001 Groups II and III vs Group I, ^{a,a}P<0.0001 Group II vs Group III.

3.3 Antioxidant enzymes activity

The mean activity of Cu/Zn SOD in the lung tissue of fluoride treated rats significantly (P<0.0001) lowered in groups II and III than the control group with respectively

decreasing -36.29% and -79.17% after 40 days of fluoride treatment (Fig. 4a). Post hoc Tukey's HSD multiple comparison test after ANOVA revealed a significant decrease (P<0.0001) in the activity of Cu/Zn

SOD between and within groups (95% CI= 1.381 to 2.047) in rats with fluoride intoxication.

The mean activity of GPx in the lung tissue of fluoridated rats declined significantly ($P < 0.0001$) in comparison with control. The decline of -31.74% in group II received 300 mg NaF/L and -66.26% in group III received 600 mg NaF/L was observed after 40 days of fluoride treatment (Fig. 4b). Post hoc Tukey's HSD multiple comparison test after ANOVA displayed a significant decrease ($P < 0.0001$) in the activity of GPx between and within groups (95% CI= 1.482 to 2.090) after 40 days of fluoride treatment.

The mean activity of CAT in the lung tissue of test rats was significantly ($P < 0.0001$) declined in groups II and III with respectively decreasing -41.46% in group II received 300 mg/L NaF and -72.53% in group III received 600 mg/L NaF as compared with control after 40 days of fluoride exposure (Fig. 4c). Post hoc Tukey's HSD multiple comparison test after ANOVA determined a significant decrease ($P < 0.0001$) in the activity of CAT between and within groups (95% CI= 0.275 to 0.262) in rats with fluoride intoxication.

Fig. 4 a-c Effect of fluoride on the mean activity of Cu/Zn SOD, GPx and CAT in lung of control and fluoride exposed rats. The values represent Mean±SD (n=6). ^a $P < 0.0001$ Groups II and III vs Group I, ^{a,a} $P < 0.0001$ Group II vs Group III.

3.4 Correlation analysis

Pearson's bivariate correlation and simple linear regression analysis showed a strong positive relationship between levels of lung tissue fluoride and MDA ($r = 0.993$, Fig. 5a) and a negative relationship between levels

of pulmonary fluoride and GSH ($r = -0.956$, Fig. 5b) along with activities of antioxidant enzymes with Cu/Zn SOD ($r = -0.996$, Fig. 5c), GPx ($r = -0.994$, Fig. 5d) and CAT ($r = -0.982$, Fig. 5e) in rats exposed to fluoride.

Fig. 5 a-e Pearson’s bivariate correlation and simple linear regression between lung fluoride and activities of various lung enzymes in rats. **a** tissue fluoride vs. MDA, **b** tissue fluoride vs. GSH, **c** tissue fluoride vs. Cu/Zn SOD, **d** tissue fluoride vs. GPx, **e** tissue fluoride vs. CAT.

3.5 Effect of NaF on the gene expression of Cu/Zn SOD, GPx and CAT

The gene expression (Fold change) of Cu/Zn SOD, GPx and CAT enzyme in the lung of control group was observed to be 1.0. β -actin was used as a housekeeping gene with product length of 505 bp. The mRNA of lung was used in the synthesis of cDNA. Gel electrophoresis results further confirm the specificity of used primers by using a single band of appropriate product length of β -actin, Cu/Zn SOD, GPx and CAT.

3.6 Quantitative Real-Time of Cu/Zn SOD, GPx and CAT gene

Relative gene expression of targeted genes was significantly ($P < 0.0001$) decreased in fluoridated groups of rats with values 0.314 ± 0.002 and 0.095 ± 0.002 (Cu/Zn SOD; Fig 6), 0.233 ± 0.009 and 0.115 ± 0.009 (GPx; Fig 6), 0.278 ± 0.015 and 0.106 ± 0.002 (CAT; Fig 6) as compared to control.

Fig. 6: Relative gene expression of Cu/Zn SOD, GPx and CAT after 40 days of exposure to fluoride in rat lung. The genes were quantified in triplicate, according to the expression related to constitutive gene β -actin. Results are expressed as mean \pm SD. One-way ANOVA followed by Post hoc Tukey’s HSD test, $P < 0.0001$ vs control.

3.7 Correlation analysis between gene expressions and levels of fluoride

Pearson's bivariate correlation and simple linear regression analysis displayed a highly significant

negative relationship between levels of fluoride and gene expression of Cu/Zn SOD ($r = -0.927$, Fig. 7a), GPx ($r = -0.880$, Fig. 7b) and CAT (-0.907 , Fig. 7c) in lung tissue of rats treated with NaF.

Fig. 7 a-c Pearson's bivariate correlation and simple linear regression between lung fluoride and gene expression of various lung enzymes in rats. a tissue fluoride vs. Cu/Zn SOD, b tissue fluoride vs. GPx, c tissue fluoride vs. CAT.

4. DISCUSSION

During present study, induction of fluorosis in rodent model was successfully demonstrated by the significant accumulation of fluoride and decrease in pulmonary tissue weight of treated rats. The exposure of fluoride initiated a complex sequence of one electron-reductions within the lung tissue of molecular oxygen, leading to the production of superoxide radicals (O_2^-) within the lung tissue which further facilitated by SOD.^[24]

In the current study, NaF disrupts the body's antioxidant defence system, leading to a significant decrease in the activities of key antioxidants such as Cu/Zn SOD, GPx, and CAT when administered with high fluoride doses of 300 and 600 mg NaF. The excessive accumulation of fluoride resulted in organ damage, which in turn interfered with various important metabolic processes, enzyme activities and production of proteins as reported by previous studies.^[25, 26] A previous study has shown that fluoride impaired the generation of oxygen radical scavengers such as SOD, GPx, GSH, and total antioxidant capacity (T-AOC) in the liver of female mice.^[27] Meanwhile, an increase in the ROS synthesis causes oxidative destruction, which is impossible to stop by the weakened antioxidant system, which results in a non-appropriate defence mechanism with an ineffective cellular redox system.^[28]

A considerable decrease in GSH levels was detected in the NaF-intoxicated rats in this investigation. Glutathione (GSH), a tripeptide that is commonly found at high concentrations inside of cells constitutes an important reducing capacity of the cytoplasm and important role in combating the cells against ROS.^[29] A study suggested that fluoride concentrations were found to decrease the GSH content in the liver of mice which is further assured by elevated levels of MDA, the biomarker of lipid peroxidation.^[30] Along with this, the activity of catalase is also diminished by the overproduction of hydroperoxides, the enzyme is unable to break due to fluoride toxicity.

MDA is considered to be an end product of lipid peroxidation and an important indicator of oxidative stress.^[31] In the current study, fluoride toxicity enhanced MDA levels and as a result, lipid peroxidation which caused damage to the lung tissue by free radical ions as a result oxidative stress. Correlation analysis has displayed a strong positive relationship between levels of fluoride and MDA and a negative correlation existed with GSH in the lung of rats exposed to fluoride. Exposure of high fluoride doses accelerates the oxidative stress reaction at a fast rate. The previous study has demonstrated the alterations caused by fluoride on the pulmonary tissue histopathologically as well as decreased the activities of

CAT and peroxidases along with elevated levels of MDA in rats.^[1]

Fluoride directly inhibits the production of proteins and nucleic acids because it is an active element and has a great propensity to bond with the divalent ions Ca²⁺ and Mg²⁺, which are essential for the activities of nucleic acid polymerases.^[32] SOD stimulates the dismutation of superoxide radicals into less toxic hydrogen peroxide and water. The overall activity of superoxide dismutase is determined by its iso-enzymes Mn-SOD and Cu/Zn SOD which plays a central role in protecting against ROS.^[33]

In the present study, expression of the genes encoding Cu/Zn SOD, GPx and CAT in groups II and III were downregulated significantly in the pulmonary tissue of fluoridated rats. The gene expression profiles of Cu/Zn SOD, GPx and CAT as well as the enzymatic activity of these enzymes were well matched. Correlation analysis has revealed a strong negative relationship between levels of fluoride and gene expression of CuZn SOD, GPx and CAT in the lung of rats with fluoride intoxication. The results of the present study are in affirmation with the research of^[34] who studied the toxic effects of sodium fluoride on the gene expression of antioxidant enzymes in the liver of mice. The mRNA expression levels of Cu/Zn SOD, GPx and catalase were lower in mice when treated with 48 mg NaF. The imbalance between the anti-oxidative function of enzymes and reactive oxygen species, which causes oxidative stress and contributes to hepatic injury, was related to the decrease in gene expression as well as activity of these antioxidants caused by sodium fluoride.

Furthermore, Dudek *et al.* (2018) suggested that, fluoride ions can damage the antioxidant defence mechanism at the cellular level in humans due to an excess of ROS when exposed to concentrations of 0.02 and 1.00 mmol/l of fluoride. This results in a decrease in the gene expression of Cu/Zn SOD. Superoxide dismutase 2, CAT, GPx 1, glutathione-disulfide reductase, or microsomal glutathione S-transferase 1 were also studied, and no statistically significant differences were observed in their expression patterns in human fibroblasts.^[35]

Previously it has reported in our study that fluoride intoxication leads to development of oxidative stress by elevated levels of MDA and reduced GSH levels in the spleen tissue of rats. A decrease in the gene expression levels of antioxidant enzymes Cu/Zn SOD, GPx and CAT as well as declined enzymatic activities were also observed in fluoridated rats which supports the present study.^[36]

Down regulation of Cu/Zn SOD expression has played an important role in exacerbation of oxidative stress in fluoride endemic areas. The results of the present study are in accordance with the study of.^[37] The isoenzyme produced by the Cu/Zn SOD gene is a homodimeric

cytosolic protein that participates in the fight against ROS, a decrease in the relative gene expression level of Cu/Zn SOD was discovered in the liver.^[34] Contradictory results have been reported in the study of^[38] where upregulation of Cu/Zn SOD and Mn-SOD was found in the human lung and liver. The relative gene expression of GPx, however, significantly increased in the pancreas, skeletal muscle, and liver of streptozotocin-induced diabetic rats, while the relative gene expression of Cu/Zn SOD and CAT significantly decreased in all of the examined organs when exposed to hyperbaric oxygen.^[22] The gene expression levels of Cu/Zn SOD and CAT in the present study are in accordance with aforementioned research, as indicated by earlier studies. The present study demonstrated that fluoride acts as an enzymatic poison, inhibiting the antioxidation function of some enzymes, which led to oxidative stress and tissue damage.^[1, 35] It suggests that the body's oxidative state and target function have an impact on the metabolic processes of the antioxidant defence system in the pulmonary tissue of rats.

5. CONCLUSION

The results of the current study exhibited that high fluoride concentrations alter the gene expression of antioxidant enzymes and some biochemical parameters by an increased production of ROS which induces oxidative stress in the pulmonary tissue of rats. The present investigation on antioxidant defence machinery provides adequate information to modulate fluoride induced tissue damage at cellular and molecular level.

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Conflict of interest statement

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

Author contributions

Dr. Shashi Aggarwal contributed to the conception and design of the research work. Dr. Sukanya Thakur performed the analysis work. She also executed the research work and prepared the manuscript.

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